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Stacking sequence determination and elastic properties identification for CFRP laminates using ultrasonic techniques

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Content

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Background

Elastic properties evaluation

Applications:

Structural design, mechanical analysis, maintenance

Issues:

- Unreliable results of C12 C66...
- Equivalent single layer assumption

Exact C_{ij} of each ply in CFRP laminates:
C11 C12 C22 C23 C55

Stacking sequence identification

Manufacture quality detection
 $[0_2/45_2/90_2/-45_2]_s$

Stacking sequence identification (C scan approach)

Bulk wave reflection at **inhomogenous** grids

3D signals interpretation

Stacking sequence identification (Fibre orientation)

(a) 2D spatial image; (b) 2D fast Fourier transform of figure (a);
(c) Fibre direction at each grid of figure (b); (d) Angle-amplitude curve

Stacking sequence identification (Double sides technique)

Angle-time images with (a) front side at top; (b) back side at top.

2D spatial images of top surfaces (a) front side at top; (b) back side at top.

	layer	angle	
Fig. (c)	1	45	
	2	90	
	3	90	
	4	-45	
	5	0	
	Fig. (b)	6	90
		7	-45
		8	90
		9	90
		10	45
Fig. (a)	11	45	
	12	90	
	13	90	
	14	-45	
	15	90	
	16	0	
	17	-45	
	18	90	
	19	90	
Fig. (d)	20	45	

Stacking sequence

Elastic properties evaluation (Experiment)

(a) Laser generation ultrasonic system; (b) Experimental dispersion curves along 0 degree in the quasi-isotropic laminate

Elastic properties evaluation (GA)

Elastic properties evaluation (quasi-isotropic laminates)

Inversed results of a **quasi-isotropic laminate** $[45/90_2/-45/0/90/-45/90_2/45]_S$

Cij/ GPa	C11	C12	C22	C23	C55
20 layers	161.81	8.04	15.63	8.34	6.31

Indirect validation

Comparison between experimental and theoretical dispersion curves of $[45/90_2/-45/0/90/-45/90_2/45]_S$ (a) 0 degree; (b) 90 degree.

Elastic properties evaluation (cross-ply laminates)

Inversed results of two **cross-ply laminates manufactured in same condition**

Cij/ GPa	C11	C12	C22	C23	C55
21 layers	147.56	7.49	12.20	7.67	8.12
16 layers	153.37	8.86	13.39	8.06	7.41

Direct validation:

Stiffness coefficients of the two laminates are close, providing decent validation of the method reliability.

Conclusions

- A **double sides C scan approach** was invented to enhance the reliability of fibre direction detection of middle layers, and enable fibre orientation visualization on the laminate surfaces.
- Instead of equivalent single layer assumption, **stiffness coefficients of each layer** were evaluated, contributing to more accurate material properties characterization.
- **Direct** and **indirect validations** were conducted successfully towards the inversion method.

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